

Percentages of rices of different plant height used as parents in crosses over a 10-year period. Eight hundred and nineteen parents used in 355 randomly selected crosses at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 7 Asian nations, 1965 through 1975.

Plant ht	Rices used (%)		
	1965–67 ^a	1970–71 ^b	1974–75 ^c
	<i>In crosses</i>		
Tall	74	57	45
Intermediate	51	39	35
Semidwarf	61	86	84
Floating/ deep water	2	1	2
	<i>As individual parents</i>		
Tall	40	30	24
Intermediate	31	22	17
Semidwarf	28	48	58
Floating/ deep water	1	–	1

^a277 rice varieties and lines used in 119 crosses.

^b351 rices used in 147 crosses.

^c191 rices used in 89 crosses.

crosses involved at least one semidwarf; and by 1974–75, semidwarf involvement had leveled off at 84% (see table).

Crosses that involved a tall variety dropped from 74% in 1965–67 to 45% in 1974–75.

The intensity of use of semidwarfs as parents increased more than the percentage of crosses involving a semidwarf. In 1965–67, 28% of the total gene pool was semidwarf, and 40% was tall. Ten years later, the percentage of semidwarf material had almost doubled and that of tall and intermediate-statured materials had dropped sharply. That indicates that breeders were increasingly crossing semidwarf parents with other semidwarfs. *W*

Adequacy and importance of resources among rice breeding programs in Asia

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A plant breeder is essentially a “genetic architect.” The tools that he uses to build new rice varieties include such resources as experimental land, greenhouses, scientific information, and

varieties with specific genetic traits to use as parents.

To determine how rice scientists perceive the limitations of such resources, IRRI surveyed 38 rice breeders at 24 research centers in 10 countries as part of a study, initiated in late 1975, of rice breeding in Asia. The project was partially funded by a research grant from The Rockefeller Foundation.

Each breeder was asked to rate the adequacy of each of 14 resource factors – considered important to rice breeding – on a scale of from one to five (1 = very adequate, 5 = very

inadequate). The resources were drawn up by plant scientists from IRRI and from national programs.

The scientists rated “personal freedom to incorporate new breeding materials, techniques, and ideas into the rice improvement program” as the most adequate, with a mean rating of 1.63 (about midway between “adequate” and “very adequate”) (see table). “Availability of genetic materials” received the second highest rating (2.03 or “adequate”). “Availability of experimental land” and “availability and quality of field labor” were also rated as

Ratings of adequacy and importance of resources that influence the work of rice breeders. Thirty-eight rice breeders at 24 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Resources	Mean rating of adequacy ^a	Importance score	
		Total ^b	Index ^c
Opportunities for specialized training or advanced education for people who work under you	3.08	49	0.32
Availability of genetic materials with specific genetic characteristics	2.03	46	0.30
Personal freedom to incorporate new breeding materials, techniques, and ideas into the rice improvement program	1.63	45	0.30
Opportunity to have breeding lines thoroughly tested under diverse pest and environmental conditions	2.91	38	0.25
Financial support	3.00	37	0.24
Scientific information resources, such as journals, books, and contact with other scientists, to use in your breeding program	2.83	32	0.21
Availability and quality of trained technical help	2.75	32	0.21
Opportunities for specialized training or advanced education	3.27	17	0.11
Opportunity to gain scientific recognition	3.13	15	0.10
Equipment and tools to use in experiments and breeding work	3.08	12	0.08
Opportunities for professional advancement	3.07	11	0.07
Experimental land	2.11	7	0.05
Transportation	3.25	5	0.03
Availability and quality of labor	2.26	2	0.01
Others (specify)	3.43	10	0.07
Av.	2.99		

^aOn a scale of from 1 to 5: 1 = very adequate at this station; 2 = adequate; 3 = intermediate; 4 = inadequate; 5 = very inadequate.

^bCalculated by assigning a weight of 4 to each factor rated as first in importance by each breeder; 3 to each factor rated second; 2 to each rated third; and 1 to each factor rated fourth. Totals for each factor were then summed. Maximum possible weight per factor was 152 (if all 38 respondents had rated one factor as first in importance).

^cCalculated by dividing total importance score by maximum possible score per factor (152). 1 = most important; 0 = least important.

fairly adequate (2.11 and 2.26, respectively).

Rated as least adequate among the factors were “opportunities for specialized training or advanced education” (3.27) and “transportation” (3.25). Other resources named by the individual rice breeders were rated as least adequate by four individual breeders (3.43). Of these, “red tape and bureaucracy” was named twice.

Each breeder then ranked the top four resources in terms of importance to the success of a breeding program. Importance scores and indices were then calculated.

Rated as most important was “opportunities for specialized training or advanced education for the people who work under you.” It received an

importance rating of 49 and an index of 0.32 (see table). The adequacy rating for this resource was 3.08 (intermediate). Second most important was “availability of genetic materials,” which breeders had rated as “adequate.” Third was “personal freedom,” the factor that received the highest average adequacy rating. “Opportunity to have breeding lines thoroughly tested under diverse pest and environmental conditions” was considered fourth most important.

Interestingly, “opportunity to gain scientific recognition” was rated as ninth in importance of the 14 factors, with a mean adequacy rating of 3.13. “Opportunity for professional advancement” was rated as 11th in importance and received an adequacy rating of 3.07. ❧

Upland rice varieties for rainfed areas of Orissa, India

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A suitable drought-resistant, high yielding rice variety is needed for the rainfed region of Orissa, particularly the southwestern districts, where drought occurs regularly. A few tall, local indica

varieties such as Saria (75 days maturity), N 22 (95 days), Dular (95–100days), and Kalakeri (85 days), are planted on more than 90% of the upland rice area but their yields are low. A few cultivars in the International Upland Rice Observational Nursery (1977) with good drought resistance and resistance to diseases such as bacterial blight and *Helminthosporium* have paved the way toward solving the problem. Promising cultures identified and proposed for multilocational tests during kharif 1978 are presented in the table. ❧

Performance of promising lines from the 1977 International Upland Rice Observational Nursery. Orissa, India.

Cultivar	Drought tolerance ^a	Maturity (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Insect and disease reactions ^a			
				GM	BB	H	SR
IR2307-217-2-3	3	108	2.2	1	3	1	1
IET 3127	1	116	2.2	3	3	1	1
IR2061-522-6-9	3	107	1.8	2	3	3	1
62-355	5	108	2.0	2	5	1	2
IR2061-465-1-5-5	5	107	1.8	2	3	1	1
Dular	3	98	1.8	3	5	3	1
DV110	1	102	1.8	2	5	5	1
IET 1444	3	99	1.8	4	5	1	3
N 22 (check)	3	95	1.5	2	7	1	0
Kalakeri (check)	3	85	1.5	2	5	3	1
Saria (check)	3	75	1.4	2	5	3	1

^aStandard Evaluation System Scale: 1 = tolerant or resistant; 9 = susceptible. GM = gall midge; BB = bacterial blight; H = *Helminthosporium*; SR = sheath rot.

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